

Archiving, sharing and discussing research data on Eastern Europe, South Caucasus and Central Asia

Data Review

Data Citation

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Abstract

The World Protests dataset is part of an international research project documenting major protest episodes worldwide since 2006 (supported by the Friedrich-Ebert-Stiftung, Initiative for Policy Dialogue and the Global Social Justice program). It is presented through an online platform that provides country-level summaries, detailed information on protest events (e.g., grievances and tactics), and references to media coverage. The dataset covers 2,800+ protest episodes across more than 100 countries between 2006 and 2020, drawing primarily on international and national media reports published online. Access is available only through the interactive platform, which allows users to search, among other things, by protest type and country; no downloadable files are provided.

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Review of the World Protests dataset

by Stas Gorelik

The World Protests dataset is part of an international research project documenting major protest episodes worldwide since 2006 (supported by the Friedrich-Ebert-Stiftung, Initiative for Policy Dialogue and the Global Social Justice program). It is accompanied by an online platform that provides country-level summaries and references to media coverage. The dataset covers 2,800+ protest episodes across more than 100 countries between 2006 and 2020, drawing primarily on international and national media reports published online.

The project's central objective is to identify broad global patterns in protest activity, including dominant grievances, targets of contention, protest methods, and outcomes. Protests are categorized thematically (for instance, economic justice, political representation, civil rights, global justice), and the accompanying materials summarize trends in protest frequency, repression, and reported achievements over time. The dataset may therefore be used for macro-level, comparative analyses of protest dynamics across regions and issue areas.

Data on protests in the post-Soviet region are available under the Europe and Central Asia section of the project website. These entries document major episodes of contention in countries such as Russia, Ukraine, Belarus, and Kyrgyzstan, typically highlighting nationally salient protest waves rather than routine or localized mobilization. For each protest episode, the dataset provides a short description and links to coverage by major international media outlets (e.g., BBC, Deutsche Welle), which serve as the primary sources for event identification and classification.

The key limitation of the project lies precisely in this design choice. The dataset focuses on very large and highly visible protest events, omitting smaller demonstrations, recurrent localized protests, and low-intensity forms of contention. It cannot be treated as a comprehensive protest-event dataset. Moreover, instead of providing systematically coded event-level variables, such as precise locations, participant counts, protest tactics, duration, or interactions with security forces, the dataset relies on external media links for substantive detail. This limits its usefulness for fine-grained quantitative analysis.

Data access: <https://www.worldprotests.org/>.

Related publications:

- Chenoweth, E. (2023). "The Role of Violence in Nonviolent Resistance." *Annual Review of Political Science*, vol. 26, no. 1, pp. 55–77.
- Ortiz, I., S. Burke, M. Berrada & H. Saenz Cortés (2021). *World Protests: A Study of Key Protest Issues in the 21st Century*. Springer International Publishing.